

ANALYSIS OF INTERMEDIATE CRACK DEBONDING FAILURE OF EXTERNALLY BONDED FRP-TO-CONCRETE JOINTS WITH ANCHORS

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ABSTRACT

This research investigates the bond behaviour of externally bonded (EB) and hybrid bonded (HB) fibre reinforced polymer (FRP) concrete joints, addressing the issue of intermediate crack debonding (ICD) in RC beams. A numerical model is proposed to simulate ICD by applying one tensile force at each FRP end and implementing different bond-slip laws. Results indicate that adding one anchor to a single-shear configuration enhanced the load capacity compared to EB strengthening, with the lower loaded end being its optimal position. Besides, adding a tensile force at the opposite end of the joint allows the FRP-concrete element to withstand higher loads.

KEYWORDS

Reinforced concrete; EBR; HB-FRP; anchors; debonding; numerical model.

INTRODUCTION

In recent times, the utilization of Fibre Reinforced Polymers (FRP) as a strengthening material for reinforced concrete (RC) structures has gained significant acceptance due to its numerous advantages compared to traditional techniques. Currently, two primary approaches have been extensively examined: the Externally Bonded reinforcement (EB), where FRP is bonded to the concrete's tensile face using a structural adhesive, and Near-Surface Mounted (NSM), which involves placing the FRP and adhesive into a groove previously cut in the concrete cover. Despite the benefits provided by FRP solutions, it is widely acknowledged that the failure of RC structures reinforced with FRP is predominantly attributed to premature debonding of the laminate from the concrete substrate before the sectional failure due to FRP rupture or concrete crushing, particularly when employing the EB technique (ACI Committee 440, 2017; Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (CNR), 2013; fib Task Group 5.1, 2019).

Debonding can be classified into two failure modes regarding its origin: intermediate crack debonding (ICD), which initiates at an intermediate section of the beam due to flexural or flexural-shear cracks and propagates towards the support, and end debonding (ED), which occurs at the termination region of the FRP reinforcement. From previous literature experiments, it is commonly observed that ICD is the predominant failure mode in flexural applications (Mazzotti et al., 2016; Oller et al., 2009). Research findings indicate that the use of different types of anchorage methods, such as mechanically fastened metallic anchors (MF-FRP), FRP anchors, hybrid anchors, Π -anchors, and U-jacket anchors, can enhance the effectiveness of elements strengthened with FRP materials by delaying debonding failure (Kalfat et al., 2018).

Regarding metallic anchorages, in the existing literature, several studies have been conducted on hybrid bonding (HB) FRP systems. HB involves both the adhesive bonding from EB and the mechanical fastening through the addition of metallic plates anchored to the substrate with bolts, providing additional resistance against debonding and contributing to the load-carrying capacity of the system.

Some research has been carried out to develop methods for predicting the bonding capacity of HB joints. Several studies have focused on investigating various factors that influence the bond strength, such as the bonded length and the number of anchors (Gao et al., 2019; Wu & Liu, 2013) or the exerted pressure on the fasteners (C. Chen et al., 2018). These investigations have led to the development of analytical, numerical and FEM models aimed at estimating the bonding capacity of the joint.

Zhang et al (2022) used the partial interaction model based on the work of Haskett et al (2008) to numerically analyse the single-shear tests performed in the work of Gao et al (2019). This methodology allows to introduce a bond-slip law that can be different for each element, which makes it suitable for predicting the bond capacity of HB single-shear specimens. The bond-slip laws obtained in (Gao et al., 2019) by fitting of the experimental results were introduced in the numerical model, resulting in a satisfactory agreement between the experimental data and the numerical simulations.

However, models based on single-shear test configurations are not suitable for predicting ICD in RC beams since the load transfer mechanism is different. In flexural applications, ICD failure occurs when the laminate is not able to transfer the increment of tensile forces between cracks. This implies the presence of pulling forces at both ends of the FRP instead of just one, as happens in the single-shear case.

In the studies conducted by Teng et al (2006) and Chen et al (2007), an analytical model was developed to investigate the behaviour of an FRP-concrete element subjected to pulling forces at both sides. The model used a bilinear and linearly softening, respectively, bond-slip law, leading to analytical equations that describe the debonding process and, thus, obtaining the bond resistance. However, analytical procedures are not suitable for including different bond-slip laws in the same specimen, which is the case of the HB system.

The objective of this study is to develop a numerical model capable of taking into account the variation of tensile forces in the FRP-concrete element between two cracks, as well as implementing different bond-slip laws at each point of the joint. With this model, the bond behaviour of the HB joint is studied considering the effect of the anchor position and the ratio between pulling forces.

NUMERICAL MODEL

Unlike a single-shear configuration, the implemented model considers two pulling forces, one at each FRP end of the strengthened element. The pulling force (P_1) simulates the resultant of tensile forces that appear in the reinforcing steel (F_s) and FRP (F_f) at each crack in the concrete beam (Figure 1). To analyse the FRP-concrete element between cracks in which the increment of tensile forces should be checked to avoid ICD, a fraction of the higher load P_1 ($\alpha \cdot P_1$) is applied to the opposite end, where $0 < \alpha < 1$. Having α equal to 0 would be the case of the single-shear test, while α equal to 1 would be a case of symmetrical loads, as for example in a pure bending zone.

Figure 1: (a) Forces in the concrete element between cracks and (b) bonded joint model for predicting ICD

The model adopts the finite differences method and is designed to solve the governing equation of the bonded joint, allowing for different types of local bond-slip laws. In this methodology, the distance between cracks (s_r), assumed as the total length of the joint (L), is divided into smaller uniform increments of length $\Delta x = L/n$ (Figure 1b), being n the total number of divisions. The approach is based on an incremental slip method able to simulate the whole loading process. The proposed model is an extension of the model presented by Gómez et al (2020) to predict the load capacity of the joint in single-shear configurations. In this study, the model considers the implementation of different bond-slip laws along the bonded length, and the addition of a tensile force in the former free end by changing the boundary condition $\varepsilon_{f,threshold}$ in Eq. (1).

$$\varepsilon_{f,threshold} = \varepsilon_{f,n} = \alpha \cdot \varepsilon_{f,0} \quad \text{Eq. (1)}$$

Starting from the higher loaded end (position $x = 0$) and progressing towards the lower loaded end ($x = L$), the procedure calculates the slip and load transmission between adjacent sections for each analysed point. At a given slip value at the higher loaded end, an iterative process is performed, which is summarized in Figure 2. $P(j,1)$ represents a lower bound value for the initial load at the loaded end during iteration j . $P(j,1)$ is used to determine the corresponding strain in the FRP (ε_f), the strain in the concrete (ε_c), and the bond-shear stress (τ) using the bond-slip law at the loaded point. At iteration j , the load, $P(j,i)$, and slip, $s(j,i)$, at each point i are calculated using Eq. (2) and Eq. (3), respectively, along the FRP towards the lower loaded end. The parameter L_{per} in Eq. (2) accounts for the length of the perimeter of the FRP reinforcement.

Figure 2: Flowchart of the numerical methodology

$$P(j, i) = P(j, i - 1) - \tau(j, i - 1) \cdot L_{per} \cdot \Delta x \quad \text{Eq. (2)}$$

$$s(j, i) = s(j, i - 1) - (\varepsilon_f - \varepsilon_c) \cdot \Delta x \quad \text{Eq. (3)}$$

Increments of P at the higher loaded end are applied until the FRP strains at the lower loaded end ($\varepsilon_{f,n}$) are equal to the boundary condition $\varepsilon_{f,threshold}$ in Eq. (1). This iterative procedure will be performed for each increment of slip at the higher loaded end until failure.

The application of the methodology is illustrated in the following example. The materials and geometrical properties of the specimen used in the calculations are reported in Table 1. These properties were gathered from the work done in (Gao et al., 2019), in which anchorages consisting of steel plates of $120 \times 60 \times 5$ mm (length \times width \times thickness) anchored with chemical bolts of diameter 8 mm, applying a torque of 15 Nm, were installed in the HB-FRP specimens (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Mechanical anchor detail

To discuss the influence of having a certain force in the opposite FRP end, two values of the α ratio (0 and 0.9) are used. The bond-slip law introduced in the model is plotted in Figure 4 along with the resulting load-slip curves.

Table 1: Material and geometrical properties

Concrete	Bonded length	L	300	mm
	Width	b_c	250	mm
	Height	h_c	150	mm
	Elastic modulus	E_c	34560	MPa
FRP	Width	b_f	50	mm
	Thickness	t_f	0.668	mm
	Sectional area	A_f	33.4	mm ²
	Elastic modulus	E_f	250000	MPa
Anchor (steel plate)	Width	b_a	60	mm

Figure 4: (a) Bond-slip law (Gao et al., 2019) and (b) respective load-slip curves for EB with $L=300$ mm, considering different force ratios α

In this investigation the bond-slip relationship is considered completely reversible until the slip reaches the ultimate value. This assumption considers that bond is still within the elastic range, but it may not be applicable in all practical scenarios where bond may get the softening stage. Nevertheless, in the case under consideration, local unloading after softening is limited to a small zone at one end of the bond length. Hence, this assumption provides a substantial simplification in the analysis without compromising accuracy significantly (Teng et al., 2006).

The load-slip curves illustrate that the presence of a force with a ratio of $\alpha = 0.9$ in the lower loaded end significantly enhanced the load capacity of the FRP-concrete element by 128%, increasing it from 32 kN to 73 kN. Since the lower load compensates for 90% of the higher load only 10% of the load must be transferred. Examination of the curves reveals that both cases $\alpha = 0$ and $\alpha = 0.9$ exhibit similar behaviour up to the maximum capacity of the single-shear scenario, approximately 30 kN. However, beyond this point, the $\alpha = 0$ case reaches a plateau followed by complete debonding, whereas the $\alpha = 0.9$ case experiences a linear increase in load until failure. Analysis of the shear stress distribution along the length at different stages (Figure 5) shows how debonding propagates towards the lower loaded end for $\alpha = 0.9$, spanning from 40 kN to 73 kN, whereas for $\alpha = 0$, the specimen cannot increase the load capacity once debonding commences at the loaded end.

Figure 5: Shear stress distributions at different stages for an EB specimen with $L=300$ mm, considering (a) $\alpha = 0$ and (b) $\alpha = 0.9$

PARAMETRIC STUDY

A parametric study is conducted to examine the impact of the ratio between pulling forces (α) and the anchor location. The material properties (Table 1) and bond-slip laws for EB and HB (Figure 6) determined by Gao et al. (2019) are utilized for this purpose. The study focuses on an FRP-concrete element that emulates a portion of a beam between cracks. Consequently, a crack spacing of 100 mm is considered, with α values of 0 and 0.7. Three anchor locations will be examined: the higher loaded end (Figure 7a), the midpoint of the element (Figure 7b), and the lower loaded end (Figure 7c). As a simplification and for a better understanding, these locations will be named as $x=0$, $x=L/2$, and $x=L$, respectively.

Figure 6: Bond-slip laws used in the parametric study (Gao et al., 2019)

Figure 7: Anchor position considered in the parametric study

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results of the parametric study are discussed in terms of load-slip curves (Figure 8). The analysis reveals that the inclusion of an anchorage (HB) significantly enhances the load capacity of the joint, irrespective of its position, for both $\alpha = 0$ (increase of 125%, 120% and 115% for $x=0$, $x=L/2$ and $x=L$, respectively) and $\alpha = 0.7$ (increase of 91%, 105% and 114% for $x=0$, $x=L/2$ and $x=L$, respectively). The

load-slip curves demonstrate higher stiffness for HB compared to EB, consistent with the ascending branch of the bond-slip law. Placing the anchor at the higher loaded end results in a stiffer behaviour compared to its placement at the lower loaded end, since, in the latter scenario, the activation of the anchor is delayed and slipping of the unanchored initial part takes place.

Figure 8: Load-slip curves for a specimen with $L=100$ mm, considering different force ratios α

In the case of $\alpha = 0$, the load capacity of HB remains relatively constant regardless of the position of the anchorage (x). However, for $\alpha = 0.7$, the load capacity of HB exhibits an upward trend with increasing position of the anchor (x). This increment can be attributed to the fact that the anchor located at the lower loaded end experiences lower stresses during the progression of slip, enabling it to contribute effectively to the load capacity once the EB is already debonded. On the other hand, if the anchor is positioned at the higher loaded end, when the anchor reaches the residual strength, the contribution of the EB at the lower loaded end is limited before complete debonding.

It can be observed that the introduction of a balancing force ($\alpha = 0.7$) has a substantial impact on the load capacity of the joint, both for EB (increase of 100%) and HB (increase of 82%, 100% and 114% for $x=0$, L and $L/2$, respectively). Interestingly, in this specific scenario, EB with $\alpha = 0.7$ exhibits a similar load capacity as HB with $\alpha = 0$.

Shear stress distribution for the case of $\alpha = 0$

Shear stress distributions at different stages for $\alpha = 0$ are plotted in Figure 9. Curves are plotted in increments of 10 kN until the maximum load of the FRP-concrete element. Firstly, it can be observed that adding one anchor delayed the softening from approximately 10 kN in EB to 30 kN in HB, regardless of the anchor position, also resulting in stiffer load-slip curves. The failure condition for EB $\alpha=0$ is that the maximum shear stress arrives at the free end of the joint ($x=100$ mm). Due to the length of 100 mm being too small to develop the full shear stresses profile, when arriving to the maximum load capacity, the shear stress in all the bonded length of the EB joint is near the shear strength value, which makes the load capacity of the specimen decrease for higher slip values. In the case of HB, the maximum load capacity is achieved when the maximum shear stress is developed at the lower loaded end of the anchor. For $x=0$, when this condition is met, the unanchored area is at its maximum shear stress. For $x=L/2$, while the anchored portion at the free end arrived at its bond strength, the area located at the loaded end is already in the softening part, resulting in a lower area under the shear stress distribution curve and thus a lower contribution in the load capacity. This is more evident in $x=L$, since all the unanchored area is located at the loaded end, being the reason for the load capacity of the joint being slightly lower when moving the anchor towards the free end. After reaching the maximum load,

the anchor stands a residual shear stress while the unanchored area is debonded, yielding to equal load capacity, regardless of the anchor position.

Figure 9: Shear stress distributions for a specimen with $L=100$ mm, with $\alpha=0$

Shear stress distribution for the case of $\alpha = 0.7$

Shear stress distributions at different stages for $\alpha = 0.7$ are plotted in Figure 10. Curves are plotted in increments of 20 kN until the maximum load of the FRP-concrete element. In this case, the failure condition for both EB and HB occurs when the point of null stresses arrives to the lower loaded end, since the equilibrium of tensile forces cannot be achieved. In the EB joint, the full shear stresses profile is developed at maximum load capacity. In HB joint, for $x=0$, once the maximum shear stress has progressed to the lower loaded end of the anchor, the anchored area can still stand some load. This results in the plateau showed in the load-slip curve (Figure 8), where the load cannot further increase because the shear stress in the anchor is reducing towards the residual strength, but part of the unanchored area is still bonded to the substrate. For $x=L/2$, at maximum load capacity (i.e. the anchored is at its maximum bond strength at the lower loaded end), the unanchored area at the higher loaded end is already debonded while the opposite side can still carry some load. Since the latter is smaller than in $x=0$, instead of a plateau it translates to a smooth transition from the loading to unloading path in the load-slip curve. For $x=L$, at the maximum load capacity the unanchored area, which is entirely located at the higher loaded end, is totally debonded while the shear stress is still progressing towards the lower loaded end. Consequently, after this point there is a sudden drop in the load-slip curve. In comparison with $\alpha=0$, where the anchor contribution at the maximum load was similar for all cases, having $\alpha=0.7$ results in a higher anchor contribution when it is far from the higher loaded end, compensating the loss of area under the curve of the unanchored part.

Figure 10: Shear stress distributions for a specimen with $L=100$ mm, with $\alpha=0.7$

CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, a numerical model based on a finite differences method has been developed to implement different bond-slip laws in a FRP-concrete element between cracks. With this model, the bond behaviour of a HB joint is studied considering the effect of the anchor position (x) in the FRP-concrete element and the ratio between pulling forces (α). The application of the methodology is illustrated through an application example with a bonded length (L) of 100 mm, an anchor width of 60 mm, three anchor positions ($x=0$, $x=L/2$ and $x=L$) and two values of α (0 and 0.7). From the results of the numerical model, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- In comparison with a single-shear case, where the force is applied only in one side of the element, adding a tensile force at the opposite end allows the FRP-concrete element withstanding higher loads, since the load to be transmitted reduces to the difference between the tensile forces at the two ends. For $\alpha = 0.7$, the load capacity of the joint increased by a 100% in EB, 82% in HB with the anchor located at $x=0$, 100% for $x=L/2$ and 114% for $x=L$.
- The introduction of an anchorage (HB) significantly enhances the load capacity of the joint, irrespective of its position, for both $\alpha = 0$ and $\alpha = 0.7$. HB technique increased the load capacity of the EB element by a 125% for $\alpha=0$ and 114% for $\alpha=0.7$.
- For low values of α , the load capacity of HB remains relatively constant for all anchor positions. However, for high values of α , which would be the case of a beam, the best location (maximum load capacity) is at the less loaded end.

CITATIONS

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All necessary data is presented in this paper.